

THE MICHAEL J. FOX FOUNDATION
FOR PARKINSON'S RESEARCH

Data-Driven Subtyping & Stratification Program

A Machine-learning Approach To Derive Biology-driven
Parkinson's Disease Subtypes And Predict Longitudinal Clinical
Outcomes Across Multiple Cohorts

Summary of Project Methods

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2. Purpose of this document

This document summarizes the theoretical rationale and methods for “A Machine Learning Approach to Derive Biology Driven Parkinson’s Disease Subtypes and Predict Longitudinal Clinical Outcomes Across Multiple Cohorts.” This project was funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation in 2023 through the Data Driven Subtyping and Stratification Program, Grant ID MJFF 023158. This technical brief is intended to help researchers understand and use the resources produced by this project in an open science context.

3. Theoretical rationale

3.1. Introduction to Parkinson's disease

PD is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the widespread intracellular accumulation of abnormal α -synuclein, leading to neuronal loss primarily in the substantia nigra. This degeneration results in a progressive dopaminergic deficiency, along with dysregulation of other neurotransmitter systems, including cholinergic, serotonergic, adrenergic, glutamatergic, and GABAergic pathways. These alterations manifest as both motor symptoms, predominantly influenced by dopamine, and non-motor symptoms.¹⁻³ In the disease's early stages, the loss of dopaminergic neurons is confined to the ventrolateral substantia nigra, while other midbrain dopaminergic neurons remain relatively intact.^{4,5} By the disease's end-stage, however, this neuronal loss is widespread. The significant neuronal depletion are found even in the early phases of the disease and indicates that degeneration in this region starts before the onset of motor symptoms, a notion supported by recent clinicopathological studies.^{6,7}

Most cases of PD are sporadic, resulting from a combination of environmental and polygenic factors, with the remaining 5-15% of cases attributed to pathogenic single gene variants.⁸⁻¹⁰ The prevalence of PD escalates with age, impacting 1% of individuals over 60 years,¹¹ and continues to trend upward through 80 years of age.^{12,13} PD shows a slight male predominance.^{13,14} However, the observed difference diminishes when accounting for age groups and geographic regions in studies,¹⁵ underscoring that it is less significant than previously anticipated. The prevalence of PD is projected to double between 2005 and 2030,¹⁶ which will lead to a substantial escalation in the disease's individual, societal, and economic impact.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ This expected rapid global increase in PD prevalence can be largely attributed to an aging population and increased longevity, however, it is also possible that environmental factors such as exposure to by-products of industrialization such as specific pesticides, solvents, heavy metals²⁰ and air pollutants^{21,22} may also play a role in this phenomenon.

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PD is diagnosed based on the presence of bradykinesia in conjunction with either rigidity or rest tremor. Additional supportive criteria, like a significant response to levodopa, are also required, and no specific exclusion criteria should be present.²³ The disease predominantly initiates with unilateral motor symptoms, maintaining asymmetry throughout its course. Most individuals with PD display non-motor symptoms such as hyposmia, autonomic dysfunction, cardiovascular issues, sleep-wake cycle disruptions and cognitive impairment. Certain non-motor symptoms may precede the motor manifestations, influencing disease progression and patients' quality of life.²⁴

To date, there are no pharmacological disease-modifying treatments for PD and its management remains largely symptomatic. Disease progression and individual patient factors largely guide therapeutic decisions. Levodopa is the cornerstone of treatment, effectively addressing motor symptoms by replenishing dopamine. However, its prolonged use can lead to motor complications, especially dyskinesias. As PD progresses, there's an increasing demand for higher levodopa doses. Dopamine agonists, while acting as alternatives or adjuncts to levodopa, have their own set of challenges as they can precipitate impulse control disorders in a significant portion of patients.²⁵

Concurrently, MAO-B and COMT inhibitors, which deter dopamine degradation, can enhance levodopa's impact. When oral therapies fall short, continuous drug delivery systems or surgical options, like deep brain stimulation, become viable. Alongside these, non-pharmacological measures, notably exercise-based therapies, play a crucial role. Additionally, multi-modal interventions are available and essential to address the prevalent non-motor symptoms accompanying PD.²⁵

3.2. Previous Parkinson's disease subtyping efforts

Increasing evidence suggests that PD may encompass multiple heterogeneous subtypes rather than representing a singular entity.^{26,27} While certain

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clinical hallmarks are frequently observed, PD often presents with a diverse spectrum of symptoms and progression trajectories. Given this heterogeneity, PD exemplifies a prime candidate for precision medicine. Here, interventions—ranging from pharmacotherapy and neurosurgery to rehabilitation—would be customized to align with an individual's unique clinical presentation, needs, and ultimately, their specific genetic or biological profile.²⁸

One example that underscores the necessity of PD subtyping is observed by the findings from two recent clinical trials. These trials, aiming to identify a disease-modifying treatment by targeting α -synuclein pathology in PD, reported negative outcomes despite no apparent flaws in their study designs. One hypothesis is that such interventions may indeed be effective, but specifically for select, as-yet-unidentified PD subtypes, rather than the broader PD population.²⁹

PD subtyping can be broadly categorized into two predominant approaches. The first, "hypothesis-driven subtyping", is rooted in direct clinical observations, reflecting the diverse clinical manifestations. In contrast, "data-driven subtyping" leverages advanced statistical and machine learning methods to identify interconnected clinical, biological, and neuroimaging parameters without predicated grouping assumptions.³⁰ Initial attempts to categorize PD in subtypes relied on clinical observation of PD symptoms over multiple visits and were hypothesis-driven. The first systematic approach to classify PD patients was proposed in 1985, suggesting two subtypes: tremor dominant and posture gait instability disorder (PIGD), derived from motor subscores on the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS).³¹ Subsequent studies, however, indicated that this subtyping approach had temporal inconsistencies or stability. Longitudinal observations of newly diagnosed and untreated PD individuals revealed frequent reclassifications between these subtypes, highlighting the unreliability of this initial classification system.³² Other examples of hypothesis-driven PD subtyping are those based on age of disease onset (early vs. late) and sex.³⁰

In a recent systematic review, data-driven subtyping emerged as the prevalent method, being adopted in 71.1% (27 out of 38) of the studied subtyping

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initiatives. Utilizing a data-driven approach facilitates the inclusion of expansive data sets and enables refined subtyping endeavors. Although studies employing this method have widened the range to cover an array of clinical aspects, reflecting the diverse nature of PD's symptoms, they also present notable methodological shortcomings that affect their clinical utility.³⁰ A primary concern lies in the heavy reliance on clinical data. Although essential, this data is vulnerable to intra-rater variability³³ and is often sourced from subjective or semi-objective scales. Even when these scales have been previously validated, a significant portion of them are often time-consuming and rely on recalled clinical manifestations, leading to potential biases.³⁴ Additionally, a lack of longitudinal evaluations in many studies, coupled with an absence of temporal stability analyses, brings into question the long-term reliability of the identified subtypes. A further drawback is observed in the significant number of studies that failed to undergo either internal or external validation, undermining the external generalizability and practical utility of the proposed subtypes. Moreover, the absence of classification algorithms for individual patients in many studies further impedes clinical application.³⁰

Given the limitations of relying heavily on clinical data for PD subtyping, integrating non-clinical data—including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and neuroimaging information—shows promise in the research community, with an increasing body of evidence supporting this approach.^{28,35,36} Existing research suggests a correlation between certain pathogenic variants and specific clinical manifestations in PD. For instance, PD patients with *LRRK2* mutations generally exhibit a slower progression of motor symptoms, while those with *GBA1* mutations have a heightened risk for cognitive decline.³⁷ Correlations have been found between blood transcriptomic profiles and clinical outcomes in deceased PD patients.³⁸ A detailed review centered on employing machine learning for the analysis of genetic and transcriptomic PD data elucidated the enhanced accuracy achieved when integrating genetic and clinical data, compared to solely clinical data. It further identified that integrating transcriptomic data significantly bolsters the differentiation of PD patients from controls and augments biomarker identification.³⁹

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In a distinct study focusing on proteomic profiling for patient subtyping, significant differences in cognitive and motor progression trajectories across subgroups were reported.⁴⁰ There's also evidence suggesting the value of incorporating neuroimaging data for a more refined PD subtyping.⁴¹

3.3. Concepts of systems biology

Systems biology can be conceived as a response to the ever-increasing data deluge stemming from the revolution in biological research. The surge in information regarding the human organism, from genetic content to metabolic processes, underscores a reality of staggering complexity. For instance, the intricate fabric of our biology comprises about 210 distinct cell types, around 35,000 genes, and a plethora of proteins and metabolites. The sheer volume and variability of these biological components necessitate an approach that doesn't merely catalog them, but seeks to understand their interactions and relationships. Given this, traditional reductionist approaches, which focus on isolated components of biological systems, are increasingly found to be inadequate to decipher the multifaceted panorama of human biology.⁴²

Many diseases arise not solely from a single gene alteration but from complex interactions among multiple molecules. To effectively understand these diseases, it's essential to analyze the entire biological system. This involves observing the interplay of pathways, networks, and cellular activities throughout the stages of a disease. Applying systems biology in medical research can enhance our comprehension of the relationship between genes and observable traits, the combined effect of environment and genetics, and lead to new findings using broad, unbiased methods.⁴³

Systems biology often delves into "omics" to comprehensively study cellular and organismal functions. These "omics" branches encompass various molecular aspects: genomics studies the entire set of DNA sequences; transcriptomics analyzes RNA or gene expression patterns; proteomics investigates the complete range of proteins; metabolomics examines cellular metabolites; while lipidomics

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focuses on lipids or fats within cells. Each provides a unique viewpoint of cellular processes, and their collective analysis paints a holistic picture of biological functions. **Figure 2** exemplifies the components of systems biology in regards to their specificity and universality.

Figure 1 - The components and levels of complexity of systems biology

At the base of the pyramid lies the core components of the cell functional organization. Universality relates to the layers of dynamic biological patterns and upper levels of biological hierarchy show complex phenomena that emerge from interactions from a series of biological factors at different levels of complexity. Extracted from Oltvai and Barabasi (2002).

PD has traditionally been viewed as a condition marked by its clinico-pathological convergence, meaning its diagnosis is conceptualized using both clinical symptoms and typical pathological findings. However, this reductionist perspective is increasingly being challenged. Clinical trials targeting this pathophysiological hallmark, specifically the intracellular accumulation of alpha-synuclein, have consistently yielded negative results despite rigorous methodology.²⁹ Given this outcome, the diverse and intricate variations observed among PD patients, the successful strides of systems biology in fields like oncology,

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particularly in cancer research, and the holistic perspective proffered by systems biology, there's a growing call among researchers to pivot towards understanding the unique biological intricacies that underpin the pathology of PD. Delving into these detailed differences may pave the way for more tailored and efficacious therapeutic strategies.³⁵ **Figure 3** illustrates the proposed shift in perspective regarding PD manifestations.

Figure 2 - Illustration of the traditional clinico-pathological perspective on PD and its evolution in the context of systems biology

A) Reductionism: the Duck of Vaucanson. This engraving of the Canard Digérateur or “Digesting Duck” illustrated the famous mechanical duck made by Jacques de Vaucanson in the 18th century, which supposedly ate grain and excreted droppings in front of an audience unaware such stool pellets were not manufactured by the contraption but placed surreptitiously. The “Duck of Vaucanson” served to illustrate Descartes view (in *De Homine*, 1662) that all animals could be reductively explained as automata. We have reductively attempted to explain the large range of clinical, pathologic, genetic, and molecular findings into a single “Duck of Parkinson,” represented by each of the wheels, levers, and pipes of a single contraption (Copyright in public domain via Wikimedia Commons). **B) Systems biology: Looks like a duck, walks like a duck, but there are differences.** Modifications of the Duck of Vaucanson illustrate the systems biology model of Parkinson diseases. It acknowledges distinctive self-regulating “mechanical” systems within each of these “birds” (distinct pathophysiological processes), yet sharing enough external and internal duck-like features to belong to the same “family” but with a phenotype shaped by the “pond where they swim” (colored circles surrounding the ducks). Each “pond” includes a combination of genetic, molecular, and environmental traits that combine in systems biology networks (shades of yellow, blue, green, and red). These “Parkinson ducks” represent an oversimplification of more complicated interactions (e.g., mosaicism might have an effect on all genetic factors, mono- and polygenic; similarly, microbiota on metagenomics, etc.). LRRK2: leucine-rich repeat kinase 2 gene;

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SNCA: alpha-synuclein gene; GBA: glucocerebrosidase gene; P-tau181: tau phosphorylated at threonine 181; α -syn fibrils: oligomeric (presumably "toxic") forms of α -synuclein; A β 1-42: amyloid beta 1-42; NF-L: neurofilament light chain. Extracted from Espay and Lang (2018).

3.4. Neuroimaging in Parkinson's disease

The primary basis for diagnosing PD has been clinical observations, rather than imaging biomarkers. Although techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET) and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) are frequently used, conventional magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has generally been of limited value in everyday clinical practice. However, recent advancements in both structural and functional MRI have increased its efficacy in detecting PD-specific changes and differentiating PD from other parkinsonian disorders⁴⁴ and to identify structural changes associated with clinical features.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ Collectively, these imaging techniques contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of PD's structural and functional alterations, thereby facilitating more informed diagnosis and treatment strategies.⁴⁸

Structural MRI, particularly volumetric MRI, has shown promise in understanding the intricacies of PD. Although it is not a definitive diagnostic tool for PD, it offers several advantages. Volumetric MRI allows for the quantitative evaluation of regional cerebral atrophy and can be particularly useful in studying gray matter integrity. Volumetric MRI has been previously utilized in PD subtyping.^{49,50} Other advanced MRI techniques have been developed to offer more specific insights into PD. For instance, diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) is sensitive to the motion of water molecules along white matter fiber tracts and has been extensively utilized to study microstructural involvement in neurodegenerative diseases like PD.⁵¹ Functional MRI (fMRI), on the other hand, captures changes in neural activity and connectivity, providing valuable information on both motor and non-motor symptoms.^{48,52} **Table 1** exemplifies the different MRI techniques that can be applied to PD.

Table 1 - MRI techniques studied in PD

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Method	Techniques	Information	Changes in PD
Structural	T1-w, T2-w, IR, MT	Morphometry	SN: variable volume changes Cortex: mild reduction in volume and thickness
Neuromelanin	Spin echo T1-w	Presence of melanin-containing cells	Reduced signal intensity
Magnetization transfer	Images with (M_T) and without (M_0) MT pulse	Degree of myelination, axonal density	Reduced MT ratio ($MTR = M_0 - M_T/M_0$)
Relaxometry	T2/T2* measurements	Brain iron	Reduced T2/T2* Increased R2/R2*
Susceptibility-weighted Diffusion	Phase images DTI	Brain iron Diffusion of water in biological tissues	Increased susceptibility due to iron load Reduced FA
Tractography	DTI	Fibre tract-specific reconstruction	Reduced probability of connections
Functional	Resting state BOLD fMRI	Functional connectivity within brain networks	Reduced FC in sensorimotor Increased FC in associative
MR spectroscopy	1H MRS ^{31}P MRS	NAA, Cho, mIns, GABA, Glx, GSH, lactate Energy metabolism: ADP, PCr/ATP	Trend for metabolite reduction Decreased ATP in midbrain
Perfusion	ASL	rCBF	Reduced in cortex, Variable in basal ganglia

1H MRS, proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy; ^{31}P MRS, phosphorus magnetic resonance spectroscopy; ADP, adenosine diphosphate; ASL, arterial spin labelling; ATP, adenosine triphosphate; BOLD, blood oxygen level-dependent contrast; Cho, choline-containing compounds; DTI, diffusion tensor imaging; FA, fractional anisotropy; FC, functional connectivity; fMRI, functional magnetic resonance imaging; Glx, glutamate/ glutamine; GSH, glutathione; IR, inversion recovery; mIns, myo-inositol; MT, magnetization transfer; MTR, magnetization transfer ratio; NAA, N-acetylaspartate; rCBF, regional cerebral blood flow; PCr, phosphocreatine; SN, substantia nigra; T2, T2 relaxation time; T2*, gradient echo T2 relaxation time; T1-w, T1-weighted; T2-w, T2-weighted; R2, T2 relaxation rate; R2*, T2* relaxation rate. Extracted from Pyatigorskaya et. al (2014).

In addition to MRI techniques, DATscan is another specialized imaging modality that has gained prominence for its role in PD diagnosis. DATscan allows for the visualization of dopamine transporter levels in the brain, offering a more targeted approach to differentiate PD from other conditions with similar symptoms. While it doesn't replace clinical diagnosis, it serves as a valuable adjunct in complex or uncertain cases, providing additional data that can guide treatment decisions.^{48,53} DATscan imaging has been previously incorporated in PD subtyping studies and are correlated with disease progression.^{54,55}

3.5. Concepts in machine learning

Machine learning (ML) is a subset of artificial intelligence that enables computers to learn from data and make decisions. In the biomedical field, ML has

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been extensively applied to various complex challenges, including diagnosis, healthcare monitoring, and medical imaging. For example, ML methods have been used to enhance the reliability, performance, predictability, diagnostic accuracy and treatments for many diseases such as different types of cancer and neurodegenerative diseases such as PD.^{56–59}

Unsupervised machine learning has gained significant attention in the biomedical field for its ability to discover hidden patterns in complex data sets. One of the key techniques within unsupervised learning is clustering, which groups similar data points together based on their features (represented in **Figure 4**).⁵⁶ Unsupervised ML uses different techniques and algorithms, being k-Means and expectation–maximization and their variations the most utilized.⁶⁰

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Figure 3 - Illustration of the usage of ML to identify clusters within groups

Extracted from: Clustering Algorithms. (2023). Machine Mantra. Retrieved September 27, 2023, from <https://machinemantra.in/clustering-algorithms/>.

4. Methodological summary

4.1. Project goals and study design

This project aimed to derive data-driven subtypes by testing multiple unsupervised ML algorithms with biological information and neuroimaging as input features and, most importantly, blinded to most clinical characteristics. We will use a replication cohort and longitudinal data to ensure reproducibility and temporal stability. A multi-step approach will be applied to select and validate the best solutions using a clinical progression multi-domain space, individual clinical features, genetic information, and fluid biomarkers. **Figure 4** provides a visual summary of the steps performed at each stage of the project.

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Figure 4 - Overall study steps and related methodology in each domain

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism, MLM: mixed linear model, GWAS: Genome-wide association studies, ROIs = Regions of interest. Figure produced by the authors.

4.2. Cohorts included

We included data from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI, <http://www.ppmi-info.org/>), the Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP, <https://pdbp.ninds.nih.gov/>), and the Isradipine Versus Placebo in Early Parkinson Disease: A Randomized Trial (STEADY-PD3, <https://amp-pd.org/unified-cohorts/steady-pd-3>). For each cohort, we extracted genomics from whole genome sequencing (WGS) and clinical data obtained through standardized ratings scales. Additionally, from PPMI and PDBP, we also obtained serum transcriptomic and volumetric structural MRI data.

For most analyses performed and planned to be executed, the PPMI cohort served as the discovery cohort, while the PDBP and STEADY cohorts were combined into a single validation cohort, when both are considered to be included. All data used in this study were accessed under signed data use agreements from each cohort. PPMI data were downloaded from LONI, its online repository

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(<https://ida.loni.usc.edu/login.jsp>) and PDBP and STEADY-PD3 data was obtained from the AMP PD platform (<https://amp-pd.org/>). Whenever needed, additional information from the PDBP cohort was obtained from the PDBP portal (<https://pdbp.ninds.nih.gov/portal>).

The PPMI is a comprehensive cohort study spearheaded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation, aimed at understanding the progression of PD through a multi-dimensional approach. The study aims to collect multifaceted data from approximately 4,000 participants across about 50 global sites. Data types encompass clinical, genetic, biological, and neuroimaging information collected from diverse cohorts, including PD patients (that are untreated by the enrollment phase), individuals with prodromal symptoms, and healthy controls. PPMI focuses on identifying and comparing progression biomarkers among these cohorts.⁶¹

The PDBP is funded by the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) and is designed to expedite the identification of biomarkers in PD for application in phase II and III clinical trials. Utilizing a consortium-based structure, the PDBP concentrates on the development of clinical and laboratory biomarkers for PD diagnosis, disease progression, and prognosis. The program adheres to standardized operating procedures and utilizes pooled reference samples to facilitate cross-study comparisons and evaluate batch effects. As of October 2014, the PDBP had initiated eleven consortium projects, seven of which were in the active recruitment and biosample collection phase, enrolling 1,082 participants and accumulating 6,898 biosamples, including DNA, RNA, whole blood, plasma, serum, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), all subjected to rigorous quality control.

STEADY-PD3 was conducted as a randomized Phase 3, 2-arm, double-blind, parallel group trial with subjects randomized to Isradipine immediate release 5 mg or matching placebo twice daily for 36 months. The primary efficacy measure was the change in the total UPDRS score in the active treatment arm versus placebo between the baseline and 36 months. If patients needed to start symptomatic therapy, they continued on their randomized treatment assignment in conjunction with the symptomatic therapy and the primary outcome was assessed in the

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medications ON state. The primary analysis was based on the intent-to-treat principle and included all subjects who had 36 month data. The study had a 95% retention rate. The study was negative for the primary outcome, showing no difference in PD symptoms over the 3 years of the study between the active and placebo arms.

4.3. Eligibility criteria

- ❖ PD participants Included in this study:
 1. PD diagnosis according to PPMI, PDBP and STEADY-PD 3's criteria
 2. Availability of at least one baseline data domain: whole genome sequencing, serum transcriptomics, or structural MRI study.

- ❖ For subtyping analyses:
 1. At most 2 years of PD duration
 2. At least one clinical domain measured at baseline and again at three years in the same domain. Eligible domains include motor function, cognition, other non motor symptoms, and motor complications.

- ❖ Autoencoder training data:
 1. PD participants included in this study who did not fit the criteria for subtyping analyses.

- ❖ Control participants (data was used to generate feature selection):
 1. Availability of baseline genomics and transcriptomics metadata.
 2. Completion of a high-quality baseline MRI study in PPMI or PDBP cohort.

5. Data domain extraction

5.1. Genomics and transcriptomics

5.1.1. Genomics

We used the AMP-PD to extract and analyse WGS data from 3274 individuals, version 4 release. This data was generated using an Illumina NovaSeq or a comparable HiSeq XTen sequencer, as detailed on the AMP-PD website (<https://www.amp-pd.org/whole-genome-data>). We selected 99 SNPs that are either associated with PD risk (90 SNPs)⁶² and PD motor, cognitive and non-motor progression (9 SNPs)^{63–65} among European populations to extract the corresponding WGS genotype data. The complete list of the included SNPs can be found in **Supplementary Table 1**. WGS genotype data were obtained and encoded additively as 0 (homozygous reference), 1 (heterozygous), or 2 (homozygous alternate) to represent the number of alternate alleles. The extraction was performed using a Jupyter notebook on the Terra cloud-native platform. Of the 99 literature-curated SNPs selected, 98 were present in the AMP-PD WGS dataset. Additionally, polygenic risk scores (PRS) were calculated for the selected SNPs using beta coefficients obtained from the literature^{62–65}. We also extracted previously reported data on pathogenic variants in LRRK2, GBA, SNCA, and PRKN genes for each cohort⁶⁶.

To control for population stratification effects in the genomic feature set, we applied a PCA-based residualization procedure to the SNP genotype matrix. Missing genotype calls were first imputed and principal component analysis (PCA) was then performed on the mean-centered and unit-scaled genotype matrix using the `prcomp` function in R, and the top 20 principal components (PCs) were retained as covariates, consistent with standard practice for capturing broad ancestry effects in genome-wide analyses [PMID16862161, PMID19543373, PMID16983374]. For each SNP, a linear regression model was fitted with the 20 PCs and an intercept as predictors, with all SNP genotype vectors regressed simultaneously. Matrix inversion was performed using the standard approach, with the Moore-Penrose

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pseudoinverse applied as a fallback when the matrix was poorly conditioned (condition number $> 10^8$). Residuals representing genotype values from which linear ancestry effects had been removed were clipped to the interval $[-10, +10]$ to prevent extreme numerical artifacts. The residualized genotypes were subsequently standardized using minor allele frequency (MAF)-based scaling, under Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium assumptions. Each SNP was mean-centered by subtracting $2p$ (where p is the MAF) and scaled by $\sqrt{2p(1-p)}$. SNPs with MAF below 0.01 or above 0.99 were flagged during quality control.

5.1.2. Serum transcriptomics

Salmon-processed RNA-seq data from 2,753 individuals were downloaded from the AMP-PD project. Samples were filtered to include only baseline visits (CLINICAL_EVENT = "BL"), with RIN values greater than 6 and a diagnosis of either PD or Control. This filtering resulted in 1,293 individuals (PDBP = 706; PPMI = 587) being retained for differential expression analysis using the DESeq2 package (v1.28.1) in the R statistical environment.^{67,68} Genes were considered differentially expressed (DEGs) if they had an FDR-adjusted p-value < 0.01 and an absolute logFC > 0.37 , which was applied as the threshold for the first dimension reduction strategy, yielding 239 genes.

The second strategy starts with functional enrichment analyses of DEGs in Gene Ontology (GO) terms, implemented using the clusterProfiler package.⁶⁹ Afterward, we used the gene set variation analysis (GSVA) to extract enrichment scores (ES) of GO terms.⁷⁰ GSVA calculates sample-wise gene set ES as a function of genes inside and outside the gene set, analogously to a competitive gene set test. Further, it estimates variation of gene set enrichment over the samples independently of any class label. Conceptually, this methodology can be understood as a change in coordinate systems for gene expression data, from genes to gene sets. Thus, GSVA ES act as proxy values of pathway activity. This strategy yielded 45 GO terms for the second dimension reduction strategy.

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The third strategy is based on reverse engineering and requires firstly the inference of transcriptional networks (TNs) centered on transcription factors (TFs) of normal blood samples.^{71,72} The TFs used for this inference are annotated by Lambert et al. 2018.⁷³ This reverse engineering were performed using the RTN package, which is designed to reconstruct and analyze TNs based on the mutual information (MI), a measure that evaluates dependencies between two random variables, using the ARACNe (Algorithm for the Reconstruction of Accurate Cellular Networks) method.^{72,74} Briefly, the regulatory structure of the network is derived by mapping significant associations between known TFs and all potential targets. Interactions below a minimum MI threshold are eliminated by a permutation step and unstable interactions are additionally removed by bootstrap to create a consensus bootstrap network. In a final step, the data processing inequality algorithm is applied with null tolerance to eliminate interactions that are likely to be mediated by another TF. Here, the number of permutations used were 5000 and the number of bootstraps were 100, with a p-value cutoff of 0.001. This resulted in 114 groups of inferred target genes associated with each TF, referred to as regulatory units or regulons, with size > 100. These regulatory units were submitted to the GSVA to obtain the ES for each regulon of the datasets.⁷⁵

Figure 5 - Representation of the differential expression (volcano plot) and the gene ontology strategies for transcriptomics feature selection

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Differential expression (left figure): this strategy compares gene activity between two groups, such as diseased vs. healthy, thus identifying genes showing significant differences in expression levels. **Gene ontology (right figure):** differentially expressed genes will be categorized using gene ontology, which categorizes genes based on their functions and processes. This analysis compares how gene groups are represented within samples and provides insights into cellular pathway activities. Figure produced by the authors.

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Figure 6 - Representation of the master regulators strategy

Master regulators: a "master regulator" is a gene or protein that controls the activity of multiple other genes or proteins within a particular biological pathway or network. This strategy employs reverse engineering to derive transcriptional networks from samples and identifies regulatory units (regulons), evaluating gene regulation and disease mechanism identification. Extracted from: Columbia Systems Biology. (2015). Columbia University. Retrieved October 8, 2023, from <https://systemsbiology.columbia.edu/news/columbia-researchers-will-use-master-regulators-to-reclassify-cancer-subtypes>.

5.2. Structural neuroimaging

All T1-weighted images were processed with the FreeSurfer image analysis suite version 7.2 using the standard *recon-all* pipeline (<http://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/>). This pipeline sequentially performed motion correction, removal of non-brain tissue through hybrid watershed/surface deformation, automated Talairach transformation, and intensity normalization. Subcortical structures were segmented using probabilistic atlas priors, followed by tessellation of the gray/white matter boundary, topology correction, and surface deformation to accurately place the boundaries at tissue intensity gradients.

Cortical surfaces were then inflated and registered to a spherical atlas based on individual folding patterns. Cortical parcellation was carried out according to the Desikan–Killiany atlas,⁷⁶ providing volumes for 34 cortical regions per hemisphere. In

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addition, 22 subcortical volumetric measures were obtained from the aseg segmentation.⁷⁷ Non-parenchymal and derived volumes were removed, including choroid plexuses, ventricles, CSF, total gray/white volumes. We further evaluated 4 brainstem substructures using Freesurfer's built in solution (<https://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/fswiki/BrainstemSubstructures>), and 26 cerebellar subregions using Cerebnet's pretrained neural network.⁷⁸ A comprehensive list of the 120 ROIs extracted can be found in **Supplementary Table 2**.

Quality control was applied systematically to all reconstructions. Each image was independently evaluated by two trained raters, who inspected skull stripping, segmentation of subcortical structures, and cortical surface placement across multiple views. Reconstructions were rated on a three-point scale, with 0 indicating failure or poor quality, 1 indicating acceptable quality despite minor errors, and 2 indicating optimal quality. To increase the homogeneity of the quality control process, all trainers were instructed using standardized material specifically developed for this project, and a subset of training images was jointly rated by all raters to harmonize evaluation criteria.

Inter-rater reliability was quantified using both overall percent agreement and Cohen's kappa coefficient, the latter accounting for chance agreement. Concordance of pass/not pass in the first run was 83.14%, while concordance of specific quality grades was 53.69%. Cohen's kappa coefficient for pass/not pass in the first run was 0.384, while the weighted Cohen's kappa coefficient for specific quality grades was 0.414. When discrepancies between the raters occurred in the first run, the case was submitted for evaluation by a third independent rater, whose judgment served as the final decision. A total of 222 (14.62%) reconstructions failed to meet acceptable standards and were excluded from further analyses.

To control for variability in regional brain volumes attributable to differences in head size, we applied intracranial volume (ICV) correction using the residuals method.⁷⁹ This procedure involved fitting linear regression models within the control

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group only, with each raw ROI volume entered as the dependent variable and ICV as the independent variable. By restricting the model to controls, the regression captured the normative scaling relationship between head size and regional brain structure in the absence of disease-related atrophy. For each participant, residuals were then derived by subtracting the ICV-predicted value from the observed ROI volume. These residuals served as the ICV-adjusted measures, representing individual deviations from the expected anatomy after accounting for normal volumetric scaling.

Variability analyses incorporated multiple complementary metrics to capture differences in dispersion between PD and control groups. For each ROI, we first calculated standard deviation (SD) and variance separately within PD and control samples, and obtained the differences by subtracting control estimates from PD values. We next computed the coefficient of variation ($CV = SD/mean$) for each ROI, again estimating group-specific values and comparing their differences to normalize dispersion by regional volume. Finally, we estimated the coefficient of partial determination (CPD) for each ROI to quantify the proportion of variance in volumetric measures explained by group membership after accounting for overall variability. ROIs were ranked according to the magnitude of variability differences across these complementary indices

To examine potential systematic differences between databases, we compared volumetric measures across the PPMI and PDBP cohorts. After quality control, ROI volumes were stratified by database, and independent two-sample *t*-tests were performed for each region to test for differences in mean volume estimates between cohorts. The only ROI with a difference in volumes means higher than 10% was the left accumbens, showing consistent findings between cohorts. We additionally compared the mean volumes in each ROI before and after visual quality control, and no differences above 1.5% in mean volumes were found.

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5.3. Clinical data

5.3.1. Primary clinical outcomes

All the included cohort studies collect comprehensive data from participants, including demographic information, comorbidities, and longitudinal clinical evaluations. These evaluations cover general neurological examinations, medication usage, and a set of validated clinical scales. Common scales used in most cohorts are the Movement Disorders Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS),⁸⁰ the modified Schwab & England Activities of Daily Living Scale,⁸¹ the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA),⁸² the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT),⁸³ the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS),⁸⁴ and the Rapid Eye Movement Behavior Disorder Questionnaire (RBDSQ).⁸⁵

The MDS-UPDRS serves as a comprehensive tool for quantifying the severity of both motor and non-motor symptoms in PD, thus playing a pivotal role in monitoring detailed disease progression.⁸⁰ The MDS-UPDRS comprises four parts: Part I assesses non motor experiences of daily living, Part II evaluates motor experiences of daily living, Part III examines motor signs on clinical examination, and Part IV addresses motor complications. Based on Part II and III, several subscores were created for further analysis:

The Modified Schwab & England Activities of Daily Living Scale assesses the ability of PD patients to perform everyday tasks, offering crucial insights into disease impact on functionality.⁸¹ The MoCA scale is a sensitive tool for evaluating multiple domains of cognition such as executive function, language, short-term memory and temporo-spatial orientation, thus serving as a potential instrument to monitor cognition in PD patients.⁸² The UPSIT is an important instrument to measure hypo or anosmia, a non-motor symptom strongly associated with PD.⁸³ The ESS and RBDSQ scales are employed to detect different aspects of sleep symptoms, which are common in PD.^{84,85}

While the PDBP also includes a behavioral, a neuropsychiatric inventory, the 39 item Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire (PDQ-39)⁸⁶, the Hamilton Anxiety Rating

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Scale (HAM-A)⁸⁷ and the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS).⁸⁸ The PPMI utilizes the Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease - Autonomic (SCOPA-AUT),⁸⁹ the short form of the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS),⁹⁰ the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI),⁹¹ the Questionnaire for Impulsive-Compulsive Disorders in Parkinson's Disease (QUIP),⁹² and other specific cognitive and neuropsychological tests. Except for patients in the STEADY-PD III cohort, patients undergo semi-annual to annual assessments using the aforementioned clinical scales and evaluations.

5.3.2. Secondary clinical outcomes

To further characterize cluster phenotypes, we extracted PPMI data on levodopa responsiveness, levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD), longitudinal deep brain stimulation (DBS) candidacy, and attainment of prespecified progression milestones⁹³. Detailed methods and code are available at the following link: <https://github.com/MJFF-ResearchCommunity/Useful-PPMI-Clinical-Codes>.

5.4. Serum and CSF biomarkers

Fluid biomarkers in PPMI provide an additional validation layer for the derived clusters. We analyzed cerebrospinal fluid and blood markers including neurofilament light chain, A β 42, A β 40, phosphorylated tau 181, total tau, alpha synuclein, hemoglobin, and GFAP. Differences in the α -synuclein seed amplification test positivity and essay reaction pharmacokinetics were also included.⁹⁴

6. Subtyping framework

We implemented an unsupervised pipeline to identify biologically informed PD subtypes associated with distinct longitudinal progression patterns. Preprocessing scripts for the input features used in this framework are available at: <https://github.com/Malta-Lab/mosaic-preprocessing>. The workflow includes three sequential stages: representation learning for dimensionality reduction, clustering, and post hoc clinical validation of the

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resulting groups. Figure 7 provides an overview of the framework. The full code is available at: <https://github.com/Malta-Lab/mosaic-pd>.

Figure 7 - Subtyping Framework example.

Subtyping framework example using autoencoder and GMM as dimensionality reduction and clustering methods, respectively. The first row shows the training of the autoencoder, using *AE train* and *AE val* sets for training and validation. The second row shows the subtype discovery process on the Discovery Cohort (PPMI in our example), using the already trained and frozen autoencoder. The third row shows the subtype validation process with the *Validation Cohort* (PDBP and Steady-PD in our example), where the complete pipeline is fixed (both dimensionality reduction and clustering), simulating individual level prediction. Solutions are deemed valuable if significant and similar patterns are present on both the discovery and validation post-hoc analysis.

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Our algorithms are carefully selected to enable them to learn patterns from a set of patients and then apply those same patterns to categorize new cases into the correct group. That is why we include methods like k-means and Gaussian Mixture Models for grouping, and PCA or UMAP for mapping data to fewer dimensions. We do not use hierarchical clustering or t-SNE because they do not allow us to place a new case using the pattern learned previously. This strategy is required to simulate case level prediction of PD subtype to unseen data.

6.1. Population definitions

- ❖ Discovery Cohort: patients used to discover the clusters, and should satisfy all inclusion criteria for subtyping analyses.
- ❖ Validation Cohort” patients used to validate the clusters, and should satisfy all inclusion criteria for subtyping analyses. This data is never used to train or adapt any algorithm, and simulate individual level prediction after the pipeline is trained. Ideally, these patients should come from a different source than Discovery Cohort, if sufficient data is available.

Autoencoder sets (only used when the dimensionality reduction method is an autoencoder):

- ❖ Autoencoder training set (*AE train*): all individuals included in this study (PD participants with WGS data available) who failed to meet further inclusion criteria. These cases were used *only* for training the autoencoder and never contributed to clustering or validation analyses.
- ❖ Autoencoder validation set (*AE val*): patients comprise the ones on both the Discovery and Validation Cohorts, and are used to validate the training of the autoencoder.

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6.2. Dimensionality Reduction

In dealing with the high-dimensional data challenges often encountered in genomics and neuroimaging, dimensionality reduction is typically required, as distances become uniform with the increasing number of features. We evaluated multiple dimensionality reduction techniques, spanning both linear and non-linear methods, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) and autoencoders.

PCA, a linear approach, projects data into a lower-dimensional space by identifying directions that capture the largest variance. Its linear nature, however, limits how well it can represent complex, nonlinear relationships.⁹⁵

UMAP was also considered for its ability to learn a reusable, lower-dimensional layout that preserves local neighborhoods. It builds a graph of nearby points in the original space and then arranges points in fewer dimensions so that those neighbor relations are kept as much as possible.⁹⁶

Autoencoders represent a more flexible, nonlinear approach, as shown in Figure 8. These neural networks compress data into a latent space through an encoder and reconstruct it through a decoder. In practice, they encourage the latent space to retain the information needed to reconstruct the input, providing a compact representation that can also be applied to new samples via the encoder.

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Figure 8 - Fluxogram of autoencoder architecture.

Autoencoder trained to reconstruct biological data: Biological features are inserted into the encoder, which compresses them into the latent space (compressed latent representation). The decoder uses this latent space to reconstruct the original features. Figure produced by the authors.

6.2.1 Autoencoder architecture

Symmetric fully connected autoencoders were constructed to extract the latent space of a given patient's input data. Hidden-layer widths were generated by iteratively dividing the input dimension by an integer divisor until the latent dimension was reached. Hyperparameters explored: (A) divisors: 2, 3, 4, 5, (B): round-up or round-down and (C): 2, 3, 5, 8, 10, 15, 20.

We tailored the decoder and loss function to the input data. When dealing with continuous values, such as volumetric neuroimaging data or log-normalized gene expression values, we used the mean squared error or mean absolute error as the reconstruction loss. When using genomic SNP data, our framework enables the use of binomial and ordinal probabilistic reconstruction, considering that features may only contain integer values of 0, 1, or 2.

We used the Adam optimizer with the following parameters: learning rate = 10^{-3} , batch size = 75, reducing the learning rate on a plateau with patience = 20, and early stopping on the validation loss with patience = 70. The training initializes with a high learning rate that decreases when there is no improvement in the

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validation loss, allowing the model to skip local optima at the beginning of the training, while still being capable of identifying nuances at later epochs.

6.2.2 Autoencoder Training protocol

- I. Training phase: Models were fit exclusively on the *AE train* set, ensuring that the future clustering pool remained unseen during weight optimization.
- II. Validation phase: After each epoch, reconstruction loss was computed on the *AE val* set. No gradients were back-propagated from this data, meaning that this data is not used to update the model, but only to evaluate its performance.
- III. Model selection: The autoencoder with the lowest validation loss was selected, and its weights were frozen for all downstream analyses.

6.2.3 Autoencoder latent space extraction

Only the encoder is used from this point forward, as there is no need to reconstruct the data anymore. The frozen encoder was applied to the Discovery and Validation cohorts to generate latent vectors, which comprise a compressed representation of the input biological data that serves as the input to the clustering algorithm.

6.3. Unsupervised Machine Learning

To effectively navigate the complexity of PD data, we used different unsupervised machine learning (clustering) techniques. These include well-established methods based on the Expectation-Maximization statistical framework, such as Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), k-Means and its variations such as k-medoids and k-medians. These methods offer computational efficiency and are adept at capturing linear relationships within the feature space. These

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techniques typically result in clusters that are hyper-spherical or hyper-ellipsoidal, depending on the constraints of the covariance matrix used.

6.4. Replication on Validation cohort

After fitting the clustering algorithm using the Discovery Cohort, the model was frozen and no longer updated. We then used the latent vectors from the Validation Cohort as inputs into the algorithm to predict its clusters. Considering both the dimensionality reduction technique and cluster algorithm are no longer updated, this process simulates an individual cluster prediction algorithm for unseen data.

6.5. Post-Hoc Analysis

Multiplicity correction tests, such as the Bonferroni method, are not applicable in our scenario, as our experiments are not independent: slight variations in hyperparameters may yield virtually identical results. Nonetheless, to limit the chances of finding a "meaningful" PD subtype that arises from random variation and extensive experimentation, we implemented the subsequent criteria to select the solutions that will proceed to post-hoc clinical analysis:

- I. Have an independent cluster solution, determined by an Adjust Rand Index (which determines how similar the cluster assignments are) lower than 95% with any other solution. This step also removes experiments with the same resulting cluster assignment - *Rationale*: several of the experiments will also result in the same cluster assignments (or extremely similar ones, with only a few patients *changing* groups), which indicates virtually the same results.
- II. All clusters must comprise at least 15% of the total Cohort Size for both Discovery and Validation Cohorts - *Rationale*: A small number of patients on a cluster is extremely difficult to validate using clinical data, as inter-person variability might result in a small cluster having significant differences in clinical variables without any PD subtype relevancy.

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6. 5. 1 Validation criteria

With our pipeline, a cluster solution is deemed valuable if it has similar clinical patterns on both cohorts. For this evaluation, relevant clinical variables are selected such as UPDRS Part III total or partial scores for motor evaluation, or MOCA for cognitive evaluation. Next, a solution is deemed valuable if:

- I. On the Discovery cohort, there is a significant ($p < 0.05$) differentiation between clusters on the clinical variable at year 3.
- II. On the Validation cohort, there is a significant ($p < 0.05$) differentiation between clusters on the clinical variable at year 3.
- III. The direction of such a significant difference is the same on the Discovery and Validation Cohorts (e.g., if Cluster 1 mean value $>$ Cluster 2 mean value on the Discovery Cohort, the same pattern should apply on the Validation Cohort).

Considering that the false-discovery rate is applied independently to the Discovery and Validation cohorts, a $p < 0.05$ in both cohorts strongly suggests that such a difference is not due to random chance.

6.6. Practical use example

Example: UMAP + GMM on genomics (PPMI as discovery; PDBP + STEADY-PD3 as validation)

Inputs

- Feature matrix: 90 literature-curated SNPs encoded as 0, 1, 2 aligned to the effect allele.
- Preprocessing: normalization.
- Dimensionality reduction: UMAP.
- Clustering: GMM.
- Prespecified year-3 outcomes for post-hoc tests: MDS-UPDRS Part III.

Step 1. Discovery preprocessing

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1. Apply the missing-data policy.
2. Apply the scaler - normalization.

Step 2. Fit UMAP on discovery

1. Default Grid: `n_neighbors` {10, 15, 30, 50}; `min_dist` {0.01, 0.1, 0.25}; `n_components` (dimensions) {3, 5, 10, 20}; `metric` {euclidean, manhattan}.
2. For each grid setting, fit UMAP on discovery only and save the reducer and the embedding.

Step 3. Fit GMM on each UMAP embedding

1. Grid: `k` (number of clusters) {2, 3, 4, 5}; `covariance_type` {diag, full, tied}; `tol` {1e-4, 1e-3, 1e-2}, `reg_covar` {1e-6, 1e-5, 1e-4}.
2. Record BIC, AIC, cluster balance, and separation (for example, silhouette on the UMAP space).
3. Discard models with any cluster < 15% of the discovery cohort.

Step 4. Select non-duplicate candidates on discovery

1. Compute pairwise Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) among remaining solutions.
2. Keep only solutions that are not near-duplicates (ARI < 0.95).

Step 5. Replicate candidates on validation

1. Apply the same preprocessing to PDBP + STEADY-PD3 (schema, missing-data policy, scaler).
2. Transform validation data with the frozen UMAP reducer (transform only).
3. Assign clusters with the frozen GMM (predict and predict_proba).
4. Verify balance again (each cluster \geq 15% of validation). Candidates failing this are marked non-replicable.

Step 6. Post-hoc clinical validation at year 3

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1. Discovery: test between-cluster differences for MDS-UPDRS Part III using the prespecified analysis plan (for example, linear models or ANCOVA adjusted for age, sex, baseline). Record p values and effect directions.
2. Validation: repeat the same tests.
3. Retain a candidate if $p < 0.05$ in discovery and $p < 0.05$ in validation with the same direction of effect.

Outputs

- Frozen artifacts: scaler, UMAP reducer (fit on discovery), GMM model (fit on discovery), and a configuration file with hyperparameters, seeds, and software versions.
- Assignments: discovery and validation labels with GMM posterior probabilities.
- Post-hoc results: effect sizes, p values, and direction consistency for year-3 outcomes.

6.7. Software and Computational Environment

All experiments—data preprocessing, model training, and clustering—were conducted in Python, leveraging GPU-accelerated deep-learning frameworks optimized for large-scale, unsupervised representation learning. Autoencoder (AE) architectures were implemented in PyTorch, with training executed on NVIDIA GPUs using CUDA for hardware acceleration. The end-to-end pipeline (dimensionality reduction → clustering → replication) was orchestrated as reproducible, version-controlled workflows to ensure methodological transparency and repeatability.

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8. Supplementary tables

Supplementary Table 1. 98 Risk and Progression SNPs extracted.

#	RSID	CHR	BP	META5_NOM_GENE	Source
1	rs114138760	1	154898185	PMVK	Nalls
2	rs35749011	1	155135036		Nalls
3	rs76763715	1	155205634	GBAP1	Nalls
4	rs6658353	1	161469054	FCGR2A	Nalls
5	rs11578699	1	171719769	VAMP4	Nalls
6	rs823118	1	205723572	NUCKS1	Nalls
7	rs11557080	1	205737739	RAB29	Nalls
8	rs4653767	1	226916078	ITPKB	Nalls
9	rs10797576	1	232664611	SIPA1L2	Nalls
10	rs76116224	2	18147848		Nalls
11	rs2042477	2	96000943	KCNIP3	Nalls
12	rs11683001	2	102396963	MAP4K4	Nalls
13	rs57891859	2	135464616	TMEM163	Nalls
14	rs1474055	2	169110394	STK39	Nalls
15	rs73038319	3	18361759	SATB1	Nalls
16	rs6808178	3	28705690	LINC00693	Nalls
17	rs12497850	3	48748989	IP6K2	Nalls
18	rs55961674	3	122196892	KPNA1	Nalls
19	rs11707416	3	151108965	MED12L	Nalls
20	rs1450522	3	161077630	NMD3	Nalls
21	rs10513789	3	182760073	MCCC1	Nalls
22	rs873786	4	925376	GAK	Nalls
23	rs34311866	4	951947	TMEM175	Nalls
24	rs4698412	4	15737348	BST1	Nalls

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25	rs34025766	4	17968811	DCAF16	Nalls
26	rs6825004	4	77110365	SCARB2	Nalls
27	rs4101061	4	77147969	FAM47E	Nalls
28	rs6854006	4	77198054	FAM47E	Nalls
29	rs356182	4	90626111	SNCA	Nalls
30	rs5019538	4	90636630	SNCA	Nalls
31	rs13117519	4	114369065	CAMK2D	Nalls
32	rs62333164	4	170583157	NEK1	Nalls
33	rs1867598	5	60137959	ELOVL7	Nalls
34	rs26431	5	102365794	PAM	Nalls
35	rs11950533	5	134199105	TXNDC15	Nalls
36	rs4140646	6	27738801	TXNDC15	Nalls
37	rs9261484	6	30108683	TRIM40	Nalls
38	rs112485576	6	32578772	HLA-DRB5	Nalls
39	rs12528068	6	72487762		Nalls
40	rs997368	6	112243291		Nalls
41	rs75859381	6	133210361	LOC105378008	Nalls
42	rs199351	7	23300049	GPNMB	Nalls
43	rs76949143	7	66009851	LINC00174	Nalls
44	rs1293298	8	11712443	CTSB	Nalls
45	rs620513	8	16697593	LOC105379297	Nalls
46	rs2280104	8	22525980	BIN3	Nalls
47	rs2086641	8	130901909	CYRIB	Nalls
48	rs13294100	9	17579690	SH3GL2	Nalls
49	rs10756907	9	17727065	SH3GL2	Nalls
50	rs6476434	9	34046391	PRSS3	Nalls
51	rs896435	10	15557406	ITGA8	Nalls
52	rs10748818	10	104015279	CUEDC2	Nalls

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53	rs72840788	10	121415685	BAG3	Nalls
54	rs117896735	10	121536327	SEC23IP	Nalls
55	rs7938782	11	10558777	RNF141	Nalls
56	rs12283611	11	83487277	DLG2	Nalls
57	rs3802920	11	133787001	IGSF9B	Nalls
58	rs76904798	12	40614434	LRRK2	Nalls
59	rs34637584	12	40734202	LRRK2	Nalls
60	rs7134559	12	46419086		Nalls
61	rs10847864	12	123326598	HIP1R	Nalls
62	rs11610045	12	133063768	FBRSL1	Nalls
63	rs9568188	13	49927732	CAB39L	Nalls
64	rs4771268	13	97865021	MBNL2	Nalls
65	rs12147950	14	37989270	MIPOL1	Nalls
66	rs11158026	14	55348869	GCH1	Nalls
67	rs3742785	14	75373034	RPS6KL1	Nalls
68	rs979812	14	88464264	GALC	Nalls
69	rs2251086	15	61997385	LOC107984782	Nalls
70	rs6497339	16	19277493	SYT17	Nalls
71	rs2904880	16	28944396	NFATC2IP	Nalls
72	rs11150601	16	30977799	SETD1A	Nalls
73	rs6500328	16	50736656	NOD2	Nalls
74	rs3104783	16	52636242	CYLD	Nalls
75	rs10221156	16	52969426	CYLD	Nalls
76	rs12600861	17	7355621	CHRNA1	Nalls
77	rs12951632	17	40741013	RETREG3	Nalls
78	rs2269906	17	42294337	UBTF	Nalls
79	rs850738	17	42434630	GRN	Nalls
80	rs62053943	17	43744203	WNT3	Nalls

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81	rs117615688	17	43798308	WNT3	Nalls
82	rs11658976	17	44866805	WNT3	Nalls
83	rs61169879	17	59917366	MED13	Nalls
84	rs666463	17	76425480	DNAH17	Nalls
85	rs1941685	18	31304318	ASXL3	Nalls
86	rs12456492	18	40673380	RIT2	Nalls
87	rs8087969	18	48683589	MEX3C	Nalls
88	rs55818311	19	2341047	SPPL2B	Nalls
89	rs77351827	20	6006041	CRLS1	Nalls
90	rs2248244	21	38852361	DYRK1A	Nalls
91	rs61863020	10	112956055	ADRA2A	Progression
92	rs382940	9	108058562	SLC44A1	Progression
93	rs6593808	1	147219250	GJAS	Progression
94	rs12037169	1	147248057	GJAS	Progression
95	rs4073509	2	192611013	AC098872.3	Progression
96	rs117239007	13	30550016	LINC00544	Progression
97	rs36082764	17	70330179	LINC00511	Progression
98	rs4721411	7	2153071	MAD1L1	Progression
99	rs10939702	4	10096692	WDR1	Progression

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Supplementary Table 2. Structural brain MRI features extracted.

#	Field name	Anatomical name
	Subcortical Structures (FreeSurfer aseg)	
1	Left.Thalamus	Left Thalamus
2	Left.Caudate	Left Caudate Nucleus
3	Left.Putamen	Left Putamen
4	Left.Pallidum	Left Globus Pallidus
5	Left.Hippocampus	Left Hippocampus
6	Left.Amygdala	Left Amygdala
7	Left.Accumbens.area	Left Nucleus Accumbens
8	Left.VentralDC	Left Ventral Diencephalon
9	Right.Thalamus	Right Thalamus
10	Right.Caudate	Right Caudate Nucleus
11	Right.Putamen	Right Putamen
12	Right.Pallidum	Right Globus Pallidus
13	Right.Hippocampus	Right Hippocampus
14	Right.Amygdala	Right Amygdala
15	Right.Accumbens.area	Right Nucleus Accumbens
16	Right.VentralDC	Right Ventral Diencephalon
17	Optic.Chiasm	Optic Chiasm
18	CC.Posterior	Corpus Callosum – Posterior
19	CC.Mid.Posterior	Corpus Callosum – Mid-Posterior
20	CC.Central	Corpus Callosum – Central
21	CC.Mid.Anterior	Corpus Callosum – Mid-Anterior
22	CC.Anterior	Corpus Callosum – Anterior
	Cortical Structures (Desikan–Killiany atlas)	
1	lh.bankssts.volume	Left Banks of the Superior Temporal Sulcus
2	rh.bankssts.volume	Right Banks of the Superior Temporal Sulcus
3	lh.caudalanteriorcingulate.volume	Left Caudal Anterior Cingulate Cortex
4	rh.caudalanteriorcingulate.volume	Right Caudal Anterior Cingulate Cortex
5	lh.caudalmiddlefrontal.volume	Left Caudal Middle Frontal Gyrus
6	rh.caudalmiddlefrontal.volume	Right Caudal Middle Frontal Gyrus

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7	lh.cuneus.volume	Left Cuneus
8	rh.cuneus.volume	Right Cuneus
9	lh.entorhinal.volume	Left Entorhinal Cortex
10	rh.entorhinal.volume	Right Entorhinal Cortex
11	lh.fusiform.volume	Left Fusiform Gyrus
12	rh.fusiform.volume	Right Fusiform Gyrus
13	lh.inferiorparietal.volume	Left Inferior Parietal Lobule
14	rh.inferiorparietal.volume	Right Inferior Parietal Lobule
15	lh.inferiortemporal.volume	Left Inferior Temporal Gyrus
16	rh.inferiortemporal.volume	Right Inferior Temporal Gyrus
17	lh.isthmuscingulate.volume	Left Isthmus of the Cingulate Cortex
18	rh.isthmuscingulate.volume	Right Isthmus of the Cingulate Cortex
19	lh.lateraloccipital.volume	Left Lateral Occipital Cortex
20	rh.lateraloccipital.volume	Right Lateral Occipital Cortex
21	lh.lateralorbitofrontal.volume	Left Lateral Orbitofrontal Cortex
22	rh.lateralorbitofrontal.volume	Right Lateral Orbitofrontal Cortex
23	lh.lingual.volume	Left Lingual Gyrus
24	rh.lingual.volume	Right Lingual Gyrus
25	lh.medialorbitofrontal.volume	Left Medial Orbitofrontal Cortex
26	rh.medialorbitofrontal.volume	Right Medial Orbitofrontal Cortex
27	lh.middletemporal.volume	Left Middle Temporal Gyrus
28	rh.middletemporal.volume	Right Middle Temporal Gyrus
29	lh.parahippocampal.volume	Left Parahippocampal Gyrus
30	rh.parahippocampal.volume	Right Parahippocampal Gyrus
31	lh.paracentral.volume	Left Paracentral Lobule
32	rh.paracentral.volume	Right Paracentral Lobule
33	lh.parsopercularis.volume	Left Pars Opercularis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
34	rh.parsopercularis.volume	Right Pars Opercularis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
35	lh.parsorbitalis.volume	Left Pars Orbitalis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
36	rh.parsorbitalis.volume	Right Pars Orbitalis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
37	lh.parstriangularis.volume	Left Pars Triangularis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
38	rh.parstriangularis.volume	Right Pars Triangularis (Inferior Frontal Gyrus)
39	lh.pericalcarine.volume	Left Pericalcarine Cortex
40	rh.pericalcarine.volume	Right Pericalcarine Cortex

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41	lh.postcentral.volume	Left Postcentral Gyrus (Primary Somatosensory Cortex)
42	rh.postcentral.volume	Right Postcentral Gyrus (Primary Somatosensory Cortex)
43	lh.posteriorcingulate.volume	Left Posterior Cingulate Cortex
44	rh.posteriorcingulate.volume	Right Posterior Cingulate Cortex
45	lh.precentral.volume	Left Precentral Gyrus (Primary Motor Cortex)
46	rh.precentral.volume	Right Precentral Gyrus (Primary Motor Cortex)
47	lh.precuneus.volume	Left Precuneus
48	rh.precuneus.volume	Right Precuneus
49	lh.rostralanteriorcingulate.volume	Left Rostral Anterior Cingulate Cortex
50	rh.rostralanteriorcingulate.volume	Right Rostral Anterior Cingulate Cortex
51	lh.rostralmiddlefrontal.volume	Left Rostral Middle Frontal Gyrus
52	rh.rostralmiddlefrontal.volume	Right Rostral Middle Frontal Gyrus
53	lh.superiorfrontal.volume	Left Superior Frontal Gyrus
54	rh.superiorfrontal.volume	Right Superior Frontal Gyrus
55	lh.superiorparietal.volume	Left Superior Parietal Lobule
56	rh.superiorparietal.volume	Right Superior Parietal Lobule
57	lh.superiortemporal.volume	Left Superior Temporal Gyrus
58	rh.superiortemporal.volume	Right Superior Temporal Gyrus
59	lh.supramarginal.volume	Left Supramarginal Gyrus
60	rh.supramarginal.volume	Right Supramarginal Gyrus
61	lh.frontalpole.volume	Left Frontal Pole
62	rh.frontalpole.volume	Right Frontal Pole
63	lh.temporalpole.volume	Left Temporal Pole
64	rh.temporalpole.volume	Right Temporal Pole
65	lh.transversetemporal.volume	Left Transverse Temporal Gyrus (Heschl's Gyrus)
66	rh.transversetemporal.volume	Right Transverse Temporal Gyrus (Heschl's Gyrus)
67	lh.insula.volume	Left Insular Cortex
68	rh.insula.volume	Right Insular Cortex
	Brainstem	
1	Medulla	Medulla Oblongata

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2	Pons	Pons
3	SCP	Superior Cerebellar Peduncle
4	Midbrain	Midbrain
	Cerebellum (CerebNet outputs)	
1	Cbm.Left.I.IV	Left Cerebellar Lobules I–IV (Anterior Lobe)
2	Cbm.Right.I.IV	Right Cerebellar Lobules I–IV
3	Cbm.Left.V	Left Cerebellar Lobule V
4	Cbm.Right.V	Right Cerebellar Lobule V
5	Cbm.Left.VI	Left Cerebellar Lobule VI
6	Cbm.Vermis.VI	Cerebellar Vermis – Lobule VI
7	Cbm.Right.VI	Right Cerebellar Lobule VI
8	Cbm.Left.CrusI	Left Cerebellar Crus I
9	Cbm.Right.CrusI	Right Cerebellar Crus I
10	Cbm.Left.CrusII	Left Cerebellar Crus II
11	Cbm.Right.CrusII	Right Cerebellar Crus II
12	Cbm.Left.VIIb	Left Cerebellar Lobule VIIb
13	Cbm.Right.VIIb	Right Cerebellar Lobule VIIb
14	Cbm.Left.VIIIa	Left Cerebellar Lobule VIIIa
15	Cbm.Right.VIIIa	Right Cerebellar Lobule VIIIa
16	Cbm.Left.VIIIb	Left Cerebellar Lobule VIIIb
17	Cbm.Right.VIIIb	Right Cerebellar Lobule VIIIb
18	Cbm.Left.IX	Left Cerebellar Lobule IX
19	Cbm.Vermis.IX	Cerebellar Vermis – Lobule IX
20	Cbm.Right.IX	Right Cerebellar Lobule IX
21	Cbm.Left.X	Left Cerebellar Lobule X (Nodulus)
22	Cbm.Vermis.X	Cerebellar Vermis – Lobule X (Nodulus)
23	Cbm.Right.X	Right Cerebellar Lobule X
24	Cbm.Vermis.VII	Cerebellar Vermis – Lobule VII
25	Cbm.Vermis.VIII	Cerebellar Vermis – Lobule VIII
26	Cbm.Vermis	Cerebellar Vermis (global)